

Patriarchal Pattern and Subjugation of Women: Reading Journey of Selected Novels of Bapsi Sidhwa

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Abstract:

Literature reflects the social, political, economic, cultural and spiritual conditions of the age in which it is written. In fact, it goes deep into the historical, sociological and political phenomena of the real life and reveals the knowledge of the real world. The writers' primary task is to examine the social human behavior in the prevailing social milieu. Malcolm Bradbury is right when he says, "Literature bears a complex relation to prevailing institution and social organizations to the general feel and texture of contemporary life".

The post-colonial literary discourse is a comprehensive mode of thought related to socio-political, socio-economic and socio-psychological dimensions of human suffering with a view to give a definite direction to the oppressed in society. The silence of the weak becomes the central voice. The average third-world woman is represented as ignorant, poor, uneducated, silent and unaware of her freedom. Hence writer's focus is on the plight of the existence of women under the burden of conventions and traditions. All across the world, especially in the Indian sub-continent, a woman has erased identity and writing for such women is an act of breaking their silence. Such insight into the marginalized self is brought out by Bapsi Sidhwa, a Parsi writer from Pakistan, who is very much a part of a patriarchal society still remaining separate from it. In *The Pakistani Bride* (1983), *The Crow Eaters* (1980), *Ice-Candy Man* (1988), and *Water* (2006), Sidhwa investigates female suffering, injustice, humiliation and exploitation of silent women.

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Sidhwa portrays a system that penetrates and permeates all layers of society and all religions. Ann Duffy rightly states: The lives of almost all women, regardless of class, caste and age, race and ethnicity, sexual orientation, ability or disability have been distorted by violence and the expectation of violence. Whether women are the actual targets of violence, live in fear of violence or live with a commitment to transcend the violence, violence permeates their life experience and sense of self."

The Pakistani Bride, Sidhwa's first book narrates the Pakistani Muslim society. The narrative is about a young Punjabi girl Zaitoon who, when her parents are killed during the partition of the country, is adopted by Qasim. Qasim, a hill tribal who belongs to a society where the rigid code of honour, isolated hills, strong kinship, and the segregation of sexes give rise to spatial divisions and act like a veil. The novel starts with the marriage of the ten-year-old Qasim to the fifteen-year-old Afshan. Afshan is married to a boy younger than herself. The novel describes women in a purdah society leading veiled lives. This purdah is not an outer garment but it means the modesty of a woman. Women are supposed to allow their men and elders to guide and guard them.

Afshan waits for the groom she has never seen but chosen for her by her elders: Afshan sat amidst the huddle of women. Her head bowed beneath a voluminous red veil; she wept softly as befitted a bride. Her heavy silver bangles, necklace, and earrings tinkled at the slightest movement. She also

wore an intricately carved nose pin. Thrice she was asked if she would accept Qasim, the son of Arbab, as her husband, and thrice an old aunt murmured yes on her behalf (8)

Afshan has been given away in marriage by her father to end an old enmity, whose sexual desires, her ten-year-old husband is incapable of satisfying, on her wedding night. This young bride finds more of a maternal role thrust upon her when she has to caress and comfort the weeping boy-husband. Later Afshan and her three children's death leaves Qasim womanless and homeless.

The second woman is Miriam in the story, who though childless finds herself in the role of surrogate mother to Zaitoon, the adopted daughter of Qasim. Mariam prepares young Zaitoon for the onset of puberty and tells her, "Now you are a woman. Don't play with boys and don't allow any man to touch you. This is why I bear a burkha...." (55). Zaitoon accompanies Miriam on her visits to her neighbours and "entering their dwellings was like stepping into gigantic wombs, the fecund, feted world of mothers and babies" (55)

Zaitoon, the other bride of Sidhwa's story, unlike Afshan, does not accept so readily. She is, moreover, unwilling to marry Sakhi to whom her father has pledged her in marriage. She pleads with her father not to force her to marry Sakhi. She even refers to marrying the jawan, the soldier who gave a lift to her and Qasim ... Her father is furious at her immodesty. A decent girl doesn't tell her father to whom he should marry her" (158). When she

continues to plead with him, he tells her that his words depend on his honour which is dearer to him than his life. "If you besmirch it, I will kill you with my bare hands." (158)

Sakhi who has seen his betrothed being helped across a bridge by the jawan, becomes furiously jealous. This jealousy mingled with sexual excitement where both sexes remain segregated, leads him to attack her on their wedding night:

He tore the ghoongat from her head and holding her arms in a cruel grip he panted inarticulate hatred into her face. Zaitoon looked at him wildly, terrified as he dragged her up and roughly yanked her red satin shirt over her head. Her arms flew to cover her breasts... Zaitoon's cries and shrieks subdued Sakhi and his anger and jealousy subsided. All her efforts to adjust are thwarted by Sakhi's possessive jealousy. In fact, her obedience, her enclosure into herself, and her withdrawal from all openness become the test of her husband's manliness. In her confinement she struggles to find a way and, in the end, runs away. The way is difficult and unfamiliar and if caught that would certainly mean death but she chooses death over this constrained hell. Carol is the only woman amongst the army officers in the cantonment. She is an American woman who fell in love with Farukh and married him but is caught up in an adulterous relationship with Mushtaq, her husband's senior officer. Farukh's jealousy destroys her sense of freedom:

It had corroded her innocence, and stripped her, layer by layer, of civilized niceties. She was frightened to see a part of herself change into a hideously vulgar person... During one of her outings with Mushtaq tribesman stares at her. This obscene stare stripped her own self. She was a cow, a female monkey, a gender opposed to that of a man-charmless, faceless, and exploitable" (120)

Thus, *The Pakistani Bride* is dealt with at three different levels-in the tribal world, in Lahore and the third, foreign world of Carol. All these three levels leave women rootless, cultureless and devoid of self. Their self is repressed, oppressed and suppressed. Their self is the object of the male gaze and their gaze is filtrated, identity erased and personality deformed.

The Crow Eaters traces the fortunes of Faredoon Junglewalla, a Parsi from central India, who journeys to Lahore at the end of the nineteenth century and spends the rest of his life there. In the Parsi Community modesty of women is prized. On seeing strangers staring at their women, "the muscles in the jaw grew tight... threw the Sikhs a fierce glance" (56).

Much later Freddie's son Billy is disconcerted when he finds that his wife's charms are open for one and all. "He wished for the tenth time if he were a Mohamedan and could cover her

up in a burqa. In *The Crow Eaters* Freddie's wife, Putli loves to behave like a good traditional wife. Her husband is modern but his modernity is troublesome to the wife: "Deep-rooted in the tradition of a wife. Walking behind her husband, their deportment was so painful to Putli as being marched naked in public" (188)

Sidhwa portrays the segregation and seclusion of women not only in Muslims but also in the Parsi Community. Putli enjoys her seclusion. It gives her comfort without feeling guilty at all. Women like Putli are used to this forced seclusion during periods of their 'uncleanliness', and 'impurity' and do not resent having to retire periodically to 'other room'.

This repression of women in the Parsi community is because of the surrounding Muslim society that compels women to depersonify themselves. It isolates them from their surroundings: In this repressed atmosphere, love grows astonishingly on nothing. It sprouts in the oddest places at the oddest times and takes the most bizarre forms. You can see the dusty toe of a woman peeking from her sandal and falling in love, even though their face and figure are veiled in purdah...volumes, inspired and beautiful, describe her unseen face ...There is no purdah at all among the Parsi- but generally, repressed air of India envelopes them. (206)

In *Ice-Candy Man*, Sidhwa concentrates on the turbulent year of partition. She conveys the traumatic experiences through the perspective of a young Parsi girl, Lenny, herself a wounded creative. She is devastated by Polio. Thus, to the disadvantage of being a female in a male world are added the physical deformity and a colonial milieu. Sidhwa tries to explore a female world marred by destructive and reductive forces of colonialism and patriarchy. Living in Muslim dominant society, Lenny becomes aware of the repression that society exercises on women. A trip with her cook Imam Din to his village, makes her realize the premium placed on modesty:

Already plasticized in the conduct they have absorbed from the village women; the girls try not to smile or giggle. They must have heard their mothers and their aunts (as I have) say: 'Hasi to Phasi'. Laugh(and), get laid. "I 'm not sure what it means- and I 'm sure they don't either - but they know that smiling before men can lead to disgrace" (55).

Lenny's world is habited by many other deprived women. The Ayah becomes a victim of rape and humiliation like numberless females at the time of partition, caught between rampant patriarchy and cruel and callus colonialism. The hands that rock the cradle are bruised, the heart tortured and the head tormented. The depressed self of a woman cannot even shatter itself to those shackles that rattle around her. Victimization is multi-ethnic, classless

and casteless. The Ice-Candy Man Says, “any man who has the money.... My cook, Wrestler, Imam Din, the knife sharpener, Collies”(24) can make women daily wedded and play with decked up bodies with ‘make-up on their faces and flowers in their hair’. Women are the most vulnerable targets of society who can be easily subjected to sexual, physical and mental violence. Susan Brown Miller observes, “For centuries in groups, in individuals, as soldiers and civilians, ordinary men have used rape to humiliate and subordinate women and to proclaim their masculine superiority and dominance to women and to other men.” Women like Ayah are left with living bodies and dead souls ‘emptied of life’ with no ‘radiance and glow’ left.

Another female is Pappoo, the daughter of Muccho and Moti. Muccho, the sweeper woman considers her young daughter to be a curse. The mother herself is a victim of patriarchal society and is filled with self-hatred. This self-hatred of the Muccho is manifested in violence against her daughter. As a result, Pappoo is married off to a middle-aged dwarf. Pappoo does not want to marry but her pleas are unheard. She is drugged and forced to accept her deformed, insane bridegroom. This is the ultimate wound that a mother can inflict on her daughter.

Lenny herself is deprived of education the doctor tells her parents: She’ll marry-have children-lead a carefree, happy life. No need to strain her with studies and exams, he advises, “thereby sealing my fate”.

The much loved and courted by a cross-section of men in Lahore, Ayah becomes “the opposite of Virgin Mary”- a whore. The violence in Lahore has changed Ayah into a mere Skelton. Abducted, raped, and forcibly married to an ice-candy man, renamed Mumtaz, Ayah has not only lost her zest for life but also her very identity. Like Zaitoon of *The Pakistani Bride*, Ayah wishes to escape, to leave Pakistan for India. Atrocities against women are neither cultural nor region specific, it cuts across the community, class or country making no distinctions. Women are battered, betted, beaten and even burnt. Women’s tale is the endless saga of heart-rendering woes and despairs. They are the victims of the familiar male psyche: the women, a spaniel, the walnut tree, the more you beat them, the better they be.

Water (2006) by Sidhwa is based on the controversial film by Deepa Mehta. Sidhwa in the novel historicizes the images, lends greater poignancy to faces and provides speech where the film must leave the women speechless. The novel presents a truthful picture of the lives of widows in colonial India. She narrates the pathetic state of a widow in the ashram of Banares. It is the story of Chuyia, a child bride who is abandoned at a widow’s ashram in Benaras after her fifty-year-old

husband Hira Lal dies. Chuyia’s mother expresses her concern about Hira Lal, her would-be son-in-law. “I ‘ve heard Hira Lal is a grandfather”.⁷

After a long illness, Hira Lal dies and Chuyia is invited to her in-law’s house. Her mother anticipated that the daughter’s widowhood would be a complete erasure of her personal, social life and so much of her own identity. Her anticipated fears about the fate of a widow in a traditional Brahmin family universalize her misery of feminine suffering:

In Brahmin culture, once widowed, a woman was deprived of her useful function in society that of reproducing and fulfilling her duties to her husband. She ceased to exist as a person; she was no longer either daughter or daughter-in-law... A woman’s sexuality and fertility, which was so valuable to her husband in his lifetime, was converted upon his death into a potential danger to the morality of the community. (24) The traditions are responsible for the misery of women. Chuyia plays with ‘her clay dolls, skipping along a path in her bare feet and collecting the berries in her skirt for her mother to pickle and felt an overwhelming surge of tenderness and longing. (5) When Chuyia’s marriage with Hira Lal is fixed ‘she has hardly any idea of what actual marriage meant. Her dreams and identity are shattered after marriage “A woman is recognized as a person only when she is one with her husband.” (8)

Traditionally a woman is not supposed to have her voice and choice outside of marriage the wife has no recognized existence in our tradition. A woman’s role in life is to get married and have sons.” (9). Chuyia is decked up in a bridal dress and make-up to look like a doll to play with. She is expected to be a doll who is dumb, dutiful, docile and a doormat. The mother-in-law is oppressive and jerks the mangalsutra off her neck, and smashes the red glass bangles from her wrist. Before the innocent child could understand the meaning of widowhood, the woman “pulled down her skirt and pulled her blouse up, Chuyia stood naked as the day she was born, staring at the vibrant little red and blue heap her clothes made”. (35)

The hypocrisy of the patriarchy erases the voice of the weak and marginalized to hide their vicious intentions in the name of widowhood. Chuyia observes all rituals like a mute spectator. But when the most oppressive and horrible ritual of shaving off her hair was carried off in the belief, “if the widow did not shave her head, every drop of water that fell upon the hair polluted the husband’s soul.”(45) Chuyia starts screaming, “Baba, don’t leave me here”. But there is nobody to respond.

The novel *Water* is not the story of Chuyia only who is a catalyst for the change in the terrible lives of widows, but it is the story of all the widows of the

patriarchal colonized society. *Water* unveils the hypocrisy and double standards of the so-called Ashrams where instead of getting social security and dignity after losing their husbands, widows are forced to lead a life of humiliation, exploitation and prostitution.

Kalyani, another young widow with a positive outlook and radical temperament comes as a ray of hope in the life for Chuyia. Kalyani denied shaving her hair but she is damned as a polluted woman, "eating with Kalyani would pollute our food (8).

Bapsi Sidhwa narrates the experiences of Chuyia, Shakuntla, Kalyani and Snehlata to capture the reduced state of these widows who have lost all sense of shame and humiliation. They have become silent spectators who are speechless and feelingless. Chuyia in, one episode in the novel, grabs a parrot and wrings his neck. Sidhwa projects her anguish and unconscious desire to crush those who have faced her to live like a recluse.

Like all Zaitoons, Ayahs, Papoos and Chuyias, women are mired deep in the rot of a repressive society. Through all these females, Sidhwa is indicting all those rituals, traditions and practices that have depressed and oppressed women and that deny them their rights even as, human beings. They not only stunt individual growth and development but deform them, restricting freedom both physically and emotionally. No wonder right from the beginning of her life, despite the strangulating strife, shattering strains, and suffocating atmosphere, she continues to drag a subdued life which one day silently takes her to doom. Finally, women are left with three options. Firstly, to succumb to the tyranny of the system called tradition. Secondly, to oppose the system, deconstruct it, and attempt an opening within the blind tunnel through suffering. As Elena J. Kalinnikova finds- 'there are no fortunate ones' (166), yet it is better to light a candle than to curse the darkness.

Destiny had little to do with it. I had to scheme like a conspirator. Destiny's job was done. I think Destiny's purpose is merely to shock us at moments into a state of awareness, those moments are milestones in between which we have to find our own ways. (192)

Women should transform the existing over-rigid divisions of gender as differences, search for new means of knowing themselves and establish a new order of values and meanings. Women should demand not only larger space within the patriarchal structures of power but envisage a thorough dismantling of these structures in ways that will yield them greater control of their lives. Since women are 'one half of the sky' transfiguring the prevailing power structures would mean 'a social revolution'.

Women are venerable to exploitation because they are submissive and emphasize compromise rather than confrontation. Women have conditioned themselves to silence their feelings, diminish their needs, erase their identity, restrict their freedom and have a firm conviction in the values of self-sacrifice and self-effacement. Having no identity of their own, they are treated like objects rather than men's property. Instead of adapting to men, women should take the initiative to restructure their lives like Zaitoon and Chuyia." Artistic works not only record the social reality of their time but in several ways transcend it to project the realm of future possibility. That is the secret of art and literature's trans-temporal and trans-spatial appeal. The creative imagination of the novelist does not imitatively reproduce the actual world of experience but it represents the vividness or the convincing quality that serves as a trigger to their creative imagination.

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